

Synthetic, Spectral and Magnetic Studies of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes of Heterocyclic Schiff Bases

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In continuation of our studies¹, we report herein the synthesis of Schiff base metal complexes of the type ML_2 , where $M = Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II} , and $L =$ Schiff base derived from 4-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-2-aminothiazole and 5-substituted-salicylaldehyde [$R = CH_3$ (A), Cl (B) and Br (C)] or β -hydroxy- α -naphthaldehyde (D). The values of Racah parameter B and C were calculated by using different fitting procedures as described by König² to study the nephelauxetic effect which describes the fact that B values lower on complexation whereas the free metal ion values are relatively higher.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are crystalline solids, soluble in chloroform and benzene. The complexes melt with decomposition above 250°. The elemental analyses data show 1:2 (M:L) stoichiometry. The monomeric nature of the complexes is indicated by the molecular weight data. Very low conductivity values in nitrobenzene solution suggest the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes exhibit 4 bands at around:

8 600, 18 000, 20 000 and 26 000 cm^{-1} . The first three bands are assigned to spin-allowed transitions, ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (ν_1), ${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (ν_3) respectively, and the intense band at $\sim 26\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=1\,000\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) may be due to ligand-metal charge transfer. The occurrence of three spin-allowed transitions suggest an octahedral geometry for the complexes³. In order to calculate the $10Dq$ value and interelectron repulsion parameters (Racah B and C) a series of fitting procedures summarised by König² was used. The nephelauxetic ratio β , Slater-Condon parameters F_2 and F_4 , Slater-Condon-Shortley parameters F^2 and F^4 were calculated^{4,5}. The nephelauxetic effect describes the fact that the B values are lowered on complexation whereas the free metal ion values are relatively high. Jorgensen⁶ attributed the nephelauxetic effect to central field covalency and symmetry restricted covalency.

The values of B (800 to 870 cm^{-1}) are less than the free metal ion (971 cm^{-1}) value and the values of β (0.8 to 0.9) indicate considerable covalent character in the metal-ligand bond. The values of B , C (3 800–3 900), β , F_2 (1 380–1 420), F_4 (110–112), F^2 (6.8×10^4), F^4 (4.9×10^4), ν_3/ν_1 (2.3), ν_2/ν_1 (1.1) and Dq/B (1.14–1.17), support the octahedral geometry of the cobalt(II) complexes. The fitting method (b) is superior one because it does not involve ν_2 . In octahedral cobalt(II) complexes the accurate location of ν_2 is not possible due to its low intensity. Therefore, the experimental accuracy of ν_2 is considerably lower than that of ν_1 and ν_3 .

The electronic spectra of the nickel(II) complexes exhibit four bands at around 8 000, 13 500, 24 000 and 26 000 cm^{-1} . The first three bands are due to spin-allowed transitions ${}^3T_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ (ν_1), ${}^3T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^3T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ (ν_3) respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry for the complexes⁷. The fourth band at $\sim 26\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=1\,000\text{ cm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) may be due to ligand-metal charge transfer.

The values of B of the complexes (in the range 800–900 cm^{-1}) are less than the free metal ion value (1 041 cm^{-1}) and the values of β (0.8 to 0.9) indicate considerable covalent character of metal-ligand bond in the complexes. The values of B , C (4 000–4 100), β , F_2 (1 350–1 480) and F_4 (107–114), F^2 (7.1×10^4) and F^4 (5.1×10^4), ν_3/ν_1 (2.9), ν_2/ν_1 (1.7), and Dq/B (1.77–1.80) are in agreement with octahedral geometry of the complexes.

From the calculation of ligand field parameters we conclude that the method (c) resulting from fitting the sum of second and third bands should be preferred (due to smaller value of δ as compared to the other methods) provided all three $d-d$ transition bands are observed.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra of the complexes show the absence of OH band (a broad and weak band at 2 900 cm^{-1} in the ligands).

indicating utilisation of OH group in M–O bond formation. The ν_{C-O} band for the complexes was observed at $\sim 1\,330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as against $\sim 1\,280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the ligands, and the ν_{C-N} mode at $\sim 1\,580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as against $\sim 1\,630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the ligands. Such shifting of ν_{C-O} towards higher frequency and lowering of ν_{C-N} in the complexes suggest coordination through oxygen of the phenolic OH group and nitrogen of the azomethine group⁸. In case of the cobalt(II) complexes a broad and weak non-ligand band is observed at 400–475 cm^{-1} which may be due to ν_{C-O-O} or ν_{C-O} ⁹. A broad and weak band at $\sim 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the nickel(II) complexes may be due to ν_{Ni-N} and ν_{Ni-O} ¹⁰.

Magnetic susceptibility: The magnetic moments of the cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.8–5.2 B.M., which support the octahedral geometry of the complexes¹¹. The magnetic moments of the nickel(II) complexes lie in the range 3.0–3.2 B.M. and suggesting an octahedral geometry¹².

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared as described earlier¹. The complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) were prepared by refluxing the metal acetate and ligand in 1 : 2 mole ratio in ethanol for about 30 min. The crystals separated on cooling were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The physical measurements were carried out as described earlier¹.

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References

1. C. K. BHASKARE and P. G. MORE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 166.
2. E. KÖNIG, *Struct. Bonding*, 1971, 9, 175.
3. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
4. E. V. CONDON and G. H. SHORTLEY, "The Theory of Atomic Spectra", Cambridge, 1963.
5. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Crystal Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962.
6. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Struct. Bonding*, 1966, 1, 3.
7. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968, p. 333.
8. J. E. KOVACIC, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1967, 23, 183.
9. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-ligand and Related Vibrations", Edward Arnold, London, 1967.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
11. R. L. CARLIN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1965, 1, 1.
12. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1965, p. 389.